

LITERARY INSTRUCTIONAL APPROACH AND COMMUNICATION SKILLS OF JUNIOR HIGH SCHOOL STUDENTS IN AN INTEGRATED HIGH SCHOOL AT BATANGAS PROVINCE, PHILIPPINES

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Literary Instructional Approach and Communication Skills of Junior High School Students in an Integrated High School at Batangas Province, Philippines

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Abstract

Communication is essential in human interaction, encoding thoughts, emotions, and behaviors for effective understanding. This study evaluates the literary instruction in Communicative Arts in English among junior high school students in a public national high school in P. Garcia District, Batangas Province. Using a descriptive approach, the study involved 9 school administrators, 24 teachers, and 220 students. Data collection employed a validated self-constructed instrument, analyzed statistically. Findings reveal that literary instructional approaches were extensively utilized, enhancing language and reader response integration. Students demonstrated an "often proficient" communication skill level, with paralinguistic being the most influential factor. School administrators and teachers strongly agreed on the importance of communication skills in delivering quality education. The study found no significant differences in assessments among respondents, but gender was a significant variable in communication proficiency. The study highlights the role of teamwork, teacher advocacy, and effective communication in shaping students' skills. The findings support the development of a goal- and service-oriented communication skills program tailored to junior high school students, focusing on teacher-student interaction, quality instruction, and practical applications. Enhancing professional development through specialized training is recommended for administrators and teachers to better equip students for complex communication challenges. Future research should explore further links between literary instruction and communicative competence, emphasizing real-world application and outcome-based strategies. A structured communication skills program will help refine instructional practices and promote academic excellence, ultimately producing well-equipped graduates for future professional endeavors.

Keywords: *literacy, instructional, communication skills, approach*

Introduction

Literary instruction in a Communication Arts English has evolved at an alarming rate since globalization has necessitated the learning of English Communication Skills in an international perspective..

The past decades in Philippine education underwent a number of challenges including the requirements of quality instruction and a move toward instructional skill teaching pendulum using variety of approaches.

The focus is then on requirements of integrating literature to communication arts and the need to provide evidence for the delivery of quality education underpinned by sound and logic of application of theory and concepts in language and literary teaching. These pave the way for the expansion using communication tools in the field of communication arts in English instruction where both qualified teachers and most students have to be familiar with. The reliance on effective instruction is not only apparent throughout the literary course and practice, but also in encoding their thoughts and feelings in the literary process of transmitting knowledge and skills and attitudes; and making attention to ways of improving the communication skills, both oral and written, of students, and specifically, junior high school students.

Appropriate and therapeutically, effective interactions between teachers and students demand an appropriate open and effective channel of communication. According to Kruijver, et al., two (2) forms of communication behavior are directed not only at meeting the cognitive and the emotional needs of students, but also are instrumental and affective communication in influencing both is directed at meeting the cognitive and literary and practical language application.

In the context of communication arts in English, interaction using communication is set within the subject content and the relationship between the teachers and students, while in the communication arts practice, it is set in the process of relationship between teachers and students to participate and negotiate in literature and communication arts classes.

Since learning is an integral, purposive process concerned with thinking, perception, organization, and insight, the student is seen as being actively involved in seeking out new information, problem solving, and referring to past experiences, hence, understanding is developed in the whole structure of a subject. The key ingredient in the process is communication which is an important element in the education process.

Teachers today are indeed faced with the challenge of using the different tools in instructing and communicating strategically that will ultimately produce quality graduates who are fit for purpose, practice, and lifelong learning.

According to Brownell, communication is also a crucial part of instruction which bridges any communication gap that may exist between the institution and the students. It is part of a teachers' responsibility to update students periodically to ease any growing

anxiety, speak to them politely and patiently and make them feel comfortable and at ease during the communication process. A teacher who is good at communicating can also get a lot more information out of the students, resulting in quicker and more effective communication process.

As cited by Obeidat, effective communication is just one of the many skills that students must master to be effective in their field. Today's graduating students should be equipped with a working knowledge of communication skills. However, the quality of the communication has a strong relationship to its effectiveness. Verbal and nonverbal communications are used by teachers and professionals every day.

Importantly, communication is an intrinsic characteristic of human nature. Nobody cannot communicate. Communication has content and value. The content regards to what was said, whilst the relationship regards as to how it was said. The nature of the relationship depends on how the two parties understand the communication sequence. Communication is never unidirectional. It is an interaction in which each sender becomes receiver and vice versa. The failure to recognize the two-way communication capability, quite often leads to negative conclusions and attitudes.

Moreover, along the way, the message sent is not the same as the message received. The decoding of the messages is based on individual factors and subjective perceptions. This fact, in conjunction with the process of feedback makes communication. It interprets something that one hears, not according to what the sender actually said but according to his own code. Particular attention should be given by the caregivers to use technical terms and medical terminology during their contact with the ill, because it is often found that the patient ascribes different interpretations to what he hears or even more, cannot understand what is meant exactly, thus increasing mental stress, that makes it more difficult to communicate with the patient.

In order for individuals to communicate effectively, effective communication skills need to be taught focusing on internal and external factors. This point may be especially important for students. First, students will benefit from a social cognitive learning experience when curriculum is developed that provides a core set of desired outcomes, and skills taught are modelled by teachers or other respected persons. Second, students will benefit from the creation of explicit performance requirements that are linked to a graded system of incentives. As students begin to learn on their own, the need for modeling by the instructor decreases. Thus, the teacher can then focus on teaching students self-reinforcement and self-evaluation skills.

However, instruction communication is an under-appreciated, often overlooked contributor to higher cost, lower quality instruction. With ever-increasing demands for improved quality and efficiency in instruction, improving communications should be an executive level imperative. Communication challenges have always carried a cost in terms of lost productivity, and insufficient time with students.

This study will help students learned how to effectively communicate, evaluate and use their critical thinking skills; and that this knowledge will be effectively applied not only in classroom situations, but also in the practice of the chosen profession in the future. The importance of communication in providing effective and quality instruction which clearly points to the need to ensure that every students are prepared and competent in communication even prior to exiting their program of study.

Research Questions

This study aims to assess the communication skills of the junior high school students of a public national high school in Batangas Province, as basis for a Proposed Communication Skills Program for Junior High School Students. Specifically, it sought to answer the following questions:

1. What is the profile of the respondents as regards their:
 - 1.1. age;
 - 1.2. gender;
 - 1.3. age range;
 - 1.4. highest educational attainment;
 - 1.5. present position; and
 - 1.6. length of service?
2. What is the extent of utilizing literary instructional approach in the teaching of Communication Arts in English?
3. What is the level of communication skills of the junior students with respect to their:
 - 3.1. oral or verbal communication;
 - 3.2. nonverbal; and
 - 3.3. paralanguage skills?
4. What are the factors that influence the communication skills of the junior high school in terms of the:
 - 4.1. teacher professional circumstance;
 - 4.2. teacher advocate;
 - 4.3. student advocate;
 - 4.4. team work; and
 - 4.5. effective communication?
5. Is there significant difference in the level of communication skills of the junior high students as self-perceived by themselves,

school administrators, and teacher respondents when group according to their profile?

6. From the findings of the study, what Proposed Communication Skills Program is offered for junior high students?

Methodology

Research Design

This study used a combination of descriptive and qualitative methods of research. Duane, et al. states that the descriptive method of research concerns the present situation, current practices, contemporary events of a group of individuals, their behavior patterns, attitudes and opinions. The analysis of the present situation may lead a Communication Skills Program for enhancing student communication and comprehension skills. Qualitative research was also used since historical data were further utilized to realize the objectives of the study.

Surveys were likewise conducted through the use of sets of validated questionnaire and interviews. The questionnaire is the most appropriate, practical, and economical tool to gather data needed in the study. The structured interview technique was also used to clarify and verify the answers of the respondents to the questionnaire.

Participants

Participants for the study are school administrators, teachers and students from P. Garcia Integrated High School in Batangas Province. The researcher has the four (4) sections in the junior high school and there were 55 sets of survey questionnaire fielded to each of the selected sections.

Table 1 presents the distribution of the respondents. The highest number of participation was by the student respondents (220 or 86.95 percent); the high school teachers (24 or 9.49 percent); and the least participation was by the school administrators (9 or 3.56 percent) or a total of 253 respondents.

Table 1. *Respondents of the Study*

	<i>F</i>	<i>%</i>	<i>Rank</i>
School Administrators	9	3.56	3
High School Teachers	24	9.49	2
Junior High School Students	220	86.95	1
	253	100.00	

Instrument

Four (4) sets of data gathering instrument are designed and the same underwent scrutiny and validation process.

As an essential tool, the researcher with the assistance of her adviser and an expert prepared the following instrument.

Part I – The Personal Profile Information Sheet which generated data on the groups of respondents with respect to their sex and civil status, age range, highest educational attainment, and number of years in present position.

Part II – Assessment on the Literary and Skills Competencies of the Junior High School Students of a public national high school in the areas of literature and communication skills in the teaching of English.

Part III – Evaluation on the Factors that Influence the Communication Skills of Junior Students covering the following four (4) phases of language teaching: listening, speaking, reading and writing to effect effective communication.

Procedure

Once the researcher was able to get the approval of her panelists as regards the proposed title of her thesis, series of research activities were undertaken to fulfill the requirements of the paper.

As shown in the Gantt Chart, as soon as the sets of survey questionnaire were completed, they underwent content validity where the researcher was more concerned with the scope and range items used to measure the expected student literature and communication skills. Since the number and type of items are adequate to measure the construct of the study, she also sought the assistance of panel of experts – a school administrator and consultant, also her adviser, a statistician, and an expert in the field of administration and education – who were given copies of the instrument and the purpose and objectives of the study. They evaluated the sets of instruments and then determined if there was a need to add, delete or change in the items after their reviews. Their comments and suggestions for improvement and for technical presentation were considered. Then, the researcher rewrote and finalized the survey questionnaire for pre-testing in a public school in Laguna which is not the setting of the study. She personally conducted the pre-survey.

Then, the results of the dry run was analyzed as to whether the groups of respondents found difficulty in answering the question taking in consideration the clarity of items, vagueness of statements, time element in answering questions, and other related problems.

Since no problems were met, the researcher upon the recommendation of her adviser, finalized the instrument and administered the same to the school administrators, teachers, and the junior students of P. Garcia Integrated High School in P. Garcia District, Batangas

Province.

Prior to this activity, she also sought approval from the Office of the Schools Division Superintendent to administer the survey to gather the much-needed data.

Data Analysis

After the retrieval of the instruments, the data were checked, classified, tabulated and analyzed for a clearer visualization and comparison of the findings. Tables were used in the presentation of the summarized data and the following tools were utilized.

Percentage. This is used to compare two or more magnitudes to determine their relationship.

Ranking. It was utilized to show the positional importance of an item to the others.

Weighted Mean. Since the responses to the item are qualitative, weighted means were assigned for quantitative analysis, and the same means were used to determine the responses that would be typical to the respondents as a group.

F-test. The study used this test to examine the significant differences among the perceived assessments of the groups of respondents.

To determine the relationship between the pre and posttest results, the Pearson’s Coefficient of Correlation (r) was utilized.

The critical F-value of .05 alpha level and different degrees of freedom (df) set the region of acceptance and rejection. Data were interpreted using the Five-Likert Scale Method as the criteria which serve as the basis for interpretation of data. The statistical tests was processed using the Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS) software.

Results and Discussion

Specific Problem No. 1. Demographic Profile of the Groups of Respondents with Regard to their: age, gender, age range, highest educational attainment, present position, and length of service?

The following demographic information as regards the personal characteristics was gathered to justify the choice of the participants in this study.

The personal characteristics of the 253 total respondents are presented with to their:

Gender

Data gathered from the surveys reported that out of the 9 school administrators, more than the majority of them (7 or 77.78 percent) are female vs. (2 or 22.22 percent) male respondents. Likewise, more than half of the teacher respondents (17 or 70.83 percent) are female vs. (7 or 29.17 percent) male participants. The same trend was found among the 220 junior students, since more female (128 or 58.18 percent) vs. (92 or 41.82 percent) are male enrollees in the junior high school of the institution under study.

Table 2. Frequency and Percentage Distribution of the Groups of Respondents Demographic Profile According to: Gender

Gender	N = 9			N = 24			N = 220			N = 253		
	School Administrators			Teachers			Junior High School Students			Total		
	F	%	R	F	%	R	F	%	R	F	%	R
Male	2	22.22	2	7	29.17	2	92	41.82	1	101	39.91	2
Female	7	77.78	1	17	70.83	1	128	58.18	2	152	60.09	1
Total	9	100.00		24	100.00		220	100.00		253	100.00	

On the whole, with a total population of 253, there were more female respondents (152 or 69.09 percent) than male respondents (101 or 39.91 percent) in this academic research. It can be deduced from these findings that the education is still dominated by female gender which support the findings of many studies on the profession of the country that there are more female school administrators than male.

Civil Status

Three (3) sets of variables are included in Table 3 with regard to the civil status of the respondents, from single, to widow/er.

A scan on the responses showed the highest portion of the school administrators (8 or 88.89 percent) were married while (1 or 11.11 percent) was single. None indicated that he/she was widow/ widower. However, from the 24 teachers, although more than the majority of them were married (15 or 62.50 percent) and (8 or 33.33 percent) were single, there was one (1 or 4.17 percent) who registered herself as widow.

From a total 220 junior students, close to 100 percent of them (209 or 95 percent) were single vs. (11 or 5 percent) were married. In total, the married status dominated the school administrators and teachers while the single status overwhelmed the junior high school students. Impliedly, from these data, it can be concluded that more than the majority of the professional respondents were not only married, but also gainfully employed and co-earners in the family.

Table 3. Frequency and Percentage Distribution of the Groups of Respondents Demographic Profile According to Civil Status

Civil Status	N = 9			N = 24			N = 220			N = 253		
	School Administrators			Teachers			Junior Students			Total		
	F	%	R	F	%	R	F	%	R	F	%	R
Single	1	11.11	2	8	33.33	2	209	95.00	2	218	86.17	1
Married	8	88.89	1	15	62.50	1	11	15.00	1	34	13.44	2
Widow/er	0	0.00	3	1	4.17	3	0	0.00	3	1	0.39	3
Total	9	100.00	24	100.00	220	100.00	253	100.00				

Age Range

Eight age bracket are presented in Table 4 which include from 20 years and below, to 51 years and above. As shown in the distribution of responses, close to the majority of the college administrators were between 36 – 40 years old (3 or 33.33 percent) and following 2 (22.23 percent) were under 31 – 35 years old. The youngest of them was 1 (11.11 percent) whose age bracket was between 26 – 30 years old while the oldest of them was also 1 (11.11 percent) from 41-45 to 51 and above years old. Considerably, younger set of teachers were registered under 26 – 30 years old (2 or 8.32 percent) and the older ones was 1 (4.17 percent) each from under 41 – 45, to 46-50 years of age. The highest number of them (10 or 41.67 percent) were between 26 – 30; and (6 or 25 percent) between 36 – 40 years of age.

Noted were also the 199 (90.45 percent) of the junior high school students whose age range was from below 20 years of age and a little percentage of them (21 or 9.55 percent) were under 20 – 25 years old. These data prove that these school administrators and teachers are quite young, performer and still gathering experience to make them more competent educators and nurturers, as well as professionals.

Table 4. Frequency and Percentage Distribution of the Groups of Respondents Demographic Profile According to Age Range

Age Range	N = 9			N = 24			N = 220			N = 253		
	School Administrators			Teachers			Junior Students			Total		
	F	%	R	F	%	R	F	%	R	F	%	R
20 years old and below	0	0.00	7.5	0	0.00	7.5	199	90.45	1	199	78.67	1
21 – 25 years old	0	0.00	7.5	2	8.33	4	21	9.55	2	23	9.09	2
26 – 30 years old	1	11.11	4.5	10	41.67	1	0	0.00	5	11	4.35	5
31 – 35 years old	2	22.22	2	4	16.67	3	0	0.00	5	6	2.37	7
36 – 40 years old	3	33.33	1	6	25.00	2	0	0.00	5	9	3.56	6
41 – 45 years old	1	11.11	4.5	1	4.17	5.5	0	0.00	5	2	7.90	3.5
46 – 50 years old	1	11.11	4.5	1	4.17	5.5	0	0.00	5	2	7.90	3.5
51 years and above	1	11.11	4.5	0	0.00	7.5	0	0.00	5	1	0.36	8
Total	9	100.00	24	100.00	220	100.00	253	100.00				

Highest Educational Attainment

A glance at Table 5 shows the five (5) range of educational attainment of the groups of respondents. From the 9 school administrators, the higher percentage of them were holders of master’s degree (5 or 50.56 percent) while two (2) (22.22 percent) each of them were either credited with units in the master’s and doctoral levels. However, a considerable number of the teachers had units in their Master’s degree (10 or 41.67 percent) and more than met the requirement for secondary level teaching. Nonetheless, a larger percentage of them have master’s degree (7 or 29.17 percent); and there were even 2 (8.33 percent) who obtained units in the doctoral level.

It is evident from these findings that a number of these administrators and teachers are not only qualified to hold their present position, but also have meet the minimum requirements set by the government on the educational qualification of the institutions’ administrative and teaching staff.

Table 5. Frequency and Percentage Distribution of the Groups of Respondents Demographic Profile According to Highest Educational Attainment

Highest Educational Attainment	N = 9			N = 24			N = 33		
	School Administrators			Teachers			Total		
	F	%	R	F	%	R	F	%	R
Bachelor’ Degree	0	0.00	4.5	5	20.83	3	5	15.56	3
Master’s Units	2	22.22	2.5	10	41.67	1	12	36.36	2
Master’s Degree	5	55.56	1	7	29.17	2	12	36.36	1
Doctoral Units	2	22.22	2.5	2	8.33	4	4	12.12	4
Doctoral Degree	0	0.00	4.5	0	0.00	5	0	0.00	5
Total	9	100.00	24	100.00	33	100.00			

Present Position

There are three (3) major groups of respondents as reported in Table 6.

The first group was the school administrators composed of the principal and department heads of the institution; the 24 teachers who are tenured and on the fulltime teaching and were also doing adjunct services for the school; and 220 junior high school students who were from Grade 7-10.

Table 6. Frequency and Percentage Distribution of the Groups of Respondents According to Present Position N = 253

Present Position	F	%	Rank
Principal and Department Heads	9	3.56	3
Teachers	24	9.49	2
Nursing Students	220	86.95	1
Total	253	100.00	

Length of Service

Table 7 presents the seven (7) range of the years the school administrators and teachers have served the School in their present capacity.

From the 9 school administrators, more than the majority of them (6 or 61.67 percent) have been administrators of the institution for the past 6 – 10 years of service. The newest in the position was 1 (11.11 percent) who has dedicated the best part of her professional life from 11–15, to 16-20 of dedicated service.

Like their administrators, the higher percentage of teacher respondents (9 or 37.50 percent) have been with the institutions for the past 6 – 10 years while 5 (20.24 percent) below 5 years and the newest in the teaching service, while the oldest were 4 (16.67 percent) who have been employed in the institutions from 16-20 years each of faithful service.

Table 7. Frequency and Percentage Distribution of the Groups of Respondents According to Length of Service in the Institution

Length Of Service	N = 9			N = 24			N = 33		
	School Administrators			Teachers			Total		
	F	%	R	F	%	R	F	%	R
Below 5 years	1	11.11	3	5	20.83	3	6	18.18	3
6 – 10 years	6	66.67	1	9	37.50	1	15	45.45	1
11 – 15 years	1	11.11	3	6	25.00	2	7	21.22	2
16 – 20 years	1	11.11	3	4	16.67	4	5	15.15	4
21 – 25 years	0	0.00	6	0	0.00	6	0	0.00	6
26 – 30 years	0	0.00	6	0	0.00	6	0	0.00	6
31 years and above	0	0.00	6	0	0.00	6	0	0.00	6
Total	9	100.00	24	100.00	33	100.00			

Notably, close to the majority of these 33 total educator respondents have served well and dedicated themselves in the practice of their profession.

Year Level of Junior High School Students

Table 8 shows the year level of the 220 total student respondents.

A look at the distribution of responses showed more than majority of them (121 or 55 percent) were in their last of the junior year while 66 (30 percent) were in their mid-junior year; and the least (33 or 15 percent) were in their initial year.

It appears that the senior junior students who were in the last year of their academic lives prominently participated in the surveys.

Table 8. Frequency and Percentage Distribution of the Groups of Respondents According to Year Level of Junior High School Students N = 220

Year Level	F	%	Rank
Grade 8	33	15.00	3
Grade 9	66	30.00	2
Grade 10	121	55.00	1
Total	220	100.00	

Specific Problem No. 2. Extent Literary Instructional Approach is Utilized in the Teaching of Communication Arts in English

Literary instructional approach plays a vital role in the effective teaching of Communication Arts subjects. This is because achieving communicative competence requires more than a knowledge in the form of language as phonology, grammar and vocabulary; and the structural knowledge of the formal system of language.

Mastering language acquisition also requires acquisition of a synthesis of different literary skills and knowledge areas in reading literary pieces and enhancing vocabulary, discussion, research, note-taking, confidence building, and fluency and body of literary works that

help students' critical thinking skills, finding information, evaluating it, and organizing it.

Using five (5) literary instructional approach as exhibited in Table 9 in the teaching of Communication Arts in English, the 9 school administrators assessed to great extent the utilization of language used (4.08 mean), reader response (3.76 mean) and structuralism (3.52 mean), but only moderately in new criticism and stylistics (3.48 and 3.44 means).

Table 9. *Extent Literary Instructional Approach is Utilized in the Teaching of Communication Arts in English*

Literary Instructional Approach	N = 9			N = 24			N = 33		
	School Administrators			Teachers			Total		
	WA	VI	R	WA	VI	R	WA	VI	R
1. New criticism	3.48	ME	4	2.80	ME	5	3.14	ME	5
2. Structuralism	3.52	GE	3	3.24	ME	4	3.38	ME	4
3. Stylistic	3.44	ME	5	3.46	ME	3	3.45	ME	3
4. Reader response	3.76	GE	2	3.90	GE	2	3.83	GE	2
5. Language used	4.08	GE	1	4.22	GE	1	4.15	GE	1
Overall Mean	3.66	GE		3.52	GE		3.59	GE	

Legend: 4.20–5.00 – Very High Extent of Implementation | 3.40–4.19 – High Extent of Implementation | 2.60–3.39 – Moderate Extent of Implementation | 1.80–2.59 – Low Extent of Implementation | 1.00–1.79 – No Implementation

While the teacher respondents also rated to great extent two (2) of the five literary approach (language used and reader response) and moderately in three (3) approaches (stylistics, structuralism and new criticism) which generated the highest means from 4.22, to 2.80.

On the whole, the obtained means of 3.66 by the school administrators; and 3.52 by the teachers under the great extent of implementation which findings show the realization that the duty and responsibility of the English teachers are both to facilitate learning by finding ways to develop students' literary and communicative skills as well as their critical skills in analysing, synthesizing, and improving their academic performance.

Specific Problem No. 3. Assessment on the Factors that Influence the Communication Skills of Junior Students

Communication is a circular process occurring within the influential educational, social and physical contexts. Its competence results from the use of a range of learned cognitive, affective and behavioral skill; and its skills influence the quality of how instruction and learning in school setting; may this be orally or verbally, non-verbal and using paralanguage approach.

Based on the results of the investigation, the researcher has arrived at the following findings on:

Oral/Verbal Communication

Under this communication skills, twenty (20) areas are covered, from can express oral/verbal thoughts and feelings within the context of the message to require practice of phatic communication to further students' communicative competence, as shown in Table 10.

An analysis of the responses showed that the 9 school administrators evaluated the level of their students' proficiency to very in 12 major areas in require practice of phatic communication to further their skills with the highest obtained mean of 4.78 which obtained value was shares in establish and maintain human contact also with 4.78; train to possess certain "relational capacities" with 4.56; and exhibit sincerity in the use of communication skills with 4.56 obtained means. They were ranked 1.5 to 4, respectively.

Other areas covered and shared in oral/verbal communication skills were also found in exhibit enhancement of oral communication skills through personal reflexivity and instruction, influence the quality of oral communication skills in instruction, improve teacher and student relationships, advocate more instructional nursing activities through appropriate and therapeutically effective instruction and include oral communication skills using verbal skills in questioning with obtained means of 4.56 each with the rank of 8. Following ranks were in Lead to orally encoding feedback response to the transmission of information from source, to the receiver, consider account of patient's cultural and moral background, need skill in opening, closing, and managing the duration of exchanges with 4.54 means each with rank 12, also on very proficient level.

The other areas covered were evaluated under often proficient level as levelled from 4.44 mean in use multi-disciplinary team approach in the effective and functioning of knowledge, skills and attitudes in oral communication, to 4.11 mean in exhibit proficiency in reading, verbal intercourse, discourse, spoken communication or 8 areas covered under the often proficient verbal interpretation.

While the majority of the areas covered were evaluated to very effective level, the teacher respondents only had two (2) areas evaluated to very proficient level in require practice of phatic communication to further teacher-student relationship with obtained mean of 4.76; and in influence the quality of oral communication skills in communicative instruction with 4.61 mean; and the remaining areas were only exhibited to the often proficient level which were shown in the obtained means from 4.40 in advocate more instructional nursing activities through appropriate and therapeutically effective instruction, to 3.99 in can express oral/verbal thoughts and feelings within the context of the message.

Table 10. *Perceived Evaluation on the Level of Communication Skills of Junior Students by the School Administrators, Teachers and Students: Oral and Verbal Communication*

A. Oral/Verbal Communication	School Administrators			Teachers			Students			Overall		
	N=9			N=24			N=220			N=253		
	WA	VI	R	WA	VI	R	WA	VI	R	WA	VI	R
1. Can express oral/verbal thoughts and feelings within the context of the message	4.22	OP	22.5	4.00	OP	23	3.35	MP	23	3.99	OP	23
2. Use patterns of behavior leading to the transmission of message using range of potential oral communication channels	4.33	OP	19.9	4.24	OP	7	3.80	OP	15	4.12	OP	12
3. Lead to orally encoding feedback response to the transmission of information from source, to the receiver	4.55	VP	12	4.08	OP	19	3.97	OP	8	4.20	OP	6
4. Observe circular process occurring within influential social and physical contexts	4.33	OP	21	4.28	OP	6	3.72	OP	16.5	4.11	OP	15
5. Result in the use of a range of:												
5.1 learned cognitive skills	4.34	OP	17	4.20	OP	9	3.47	MP	21	4.00	OP	21
5.2 affective skills	4.53	VP	5	4.20	OP	9	3.80	OP	14	4.19	OP	9
5.3 behavioral skills	4.34	OP	17	4.20	OP	9	3.75	OP	16.5	4.10	OP	18
6. Exhibit enhancement of oral communication skills through personal reflexivity and instruction	4.56	VP	8	4.04	OP	21	3.55	OP	20	4.05	OP	19
7. Influence the quality of oral communication skills in communicative instruction	4.56	VP	8	4.12	OP	15	3.85	OP	12	4.18	OP	11
8. Direct oral communications at meeting the functional and affective needs of the students	4.23	OP	22.5	4.16	OP	12	3.95	OP	7	4.11	OP	15
9. Can elicit emotional comfort or discomfort	4.34	OP	19.5	4.12	OP	16	3.87	OP	11	4.11	OP	15
10. Consider account of students' cultural and moral background	4.56	VP	12	4.04	OP	19	3.89	OP	10	4.16	OP	13
11. Use multi-disciplinary team approach in the effective and functioning of knowledge, skills and attitudes in oral communication	4.67	VP	14	4.36	OP	4	3.99	OP	5	4.34	OP	4
12. Exhibit proficiency in reading, verbal intercourse, discourse, spoken communication	4.11	OP	24	3.96	OP	24	3.31	MP	24	3.79	OP	24
13. Improve teacher-student relationships	4.56	VP	8	4.16	OP	13	3.90	OP	9	4.21	OP	6
14. Advocate more instructional activities through appropriate and therapeutically effective instruction	4.56	VP	8	4.40	OP	3	3.82	OP	13	4.26	OP	9
15. Include oral communication skills using verbal skills in:												
15.1 questioning	4.56	VP	8	4.12	OP	14	3.64	OP	19	4.11	OP	15
15.2 explaining	4.44	OP	15	4.36	OP	19	3.44	MP	22	4.08	OP	11
15.3 reflecting and paraphrasing	4.34	OP	17	4.08	OP	17	3.70	OP	18	4.04	OP	20
16. Need skill in opening, closing, and managing the duration of exchanges	4.56	VP	8	4.00	OP	22	4.00	OP	4	4.19	OP	9
17. Train to possess certain "relational capacities"	4.67	VP	3	4.60	VP	2	3.98	OP	6	4.42	OP	2
18. Exhibit sincerity in the use of communication skills	4.56	VP	8	4.28	OP	5	4.12	OP	1	4.32	OP	5
19. Establish and maintain human contact	4.78	VP	1.5	4.20	OP	11	4.09	OP	2	4.36	OP	3
20. Require practice of phatic communication to further nurse-patient relationship	4.78	VP	1.5	4.76	VP	1	4.07	OP	3	4.54	VP	1
Overall	4.48	OP		4.21	OP		3.79	OP		4.17	OP	

Legend: 4.50-5.00 – Very Proficient (VP) | 3.50-4.49 – Often Proficient (OP) | 2.50-3.49 – Moderately Proficient (MP) | 1.50-2.49 – Least Proficient (LP) | 1.00-1.49 – Not Proficient (NP)

Finally, the student respondents evaluated their oral/ verbal communication to often proficient level in 16 major areas, from 4.12 mean in exhibit sincerity in the use of communication skills, to 3.55 mean in exhibit enhancement of oral communication skills through personal reflexivity and instruction, and moderately in the four (4) major areas under oral/verbal communication.

The evaluation results from the school administrators with overall mean of 4.48; the faculty with 4.19, and student respondents with 3.79 manifest evidence of strong and shared assessments that this aspect of communication skills required among junior student are needs that have to be addressed as strongly pointed out by Barrientos and Garin (2012).

Non-verbal Communication

Table 11 reports on the findings on the 10 areas under non-verbal communication.

A scrutiny of the distribution of responses of the three (3) groups of respondents reveals different levels of competency.

For example, while the school administrators had five (5) areas assessed to very proficient level in include the family and "significant

others” with 4.67, observe congruence of normative ways of thinking and behaving and use touch and body language approach with 4.56, do not use abbreviation, jargon, meaningless phrases, irrelevant recording and communication tools in reporting methods with 4.55 each, ranked from 1 to 4.5, respectively. The other areas covered were only rated to often proficient level by both the school administrators and the teacher respondents.

The second group had all the areas covered to often proficient level, from include the family and “significant others” with 4.36, to exhibit effective and efficient communication process in: in preparing report and recording with 3.88, but the student respondents had only evaluated their level of communicative competence to often proficient in five (5) areas and the other five (5) with their subareas to moderate level.

On the whole, the overall obtained means of 4.37 by the school administrators and 4.10 by the teachers were under the often level of evaluation. However, the findings for the students respondents were only moderate evidenced by overall obtained means of 3.48.

These differences in the level of competency very strongly point to what Obeidat (2016) articulated on the deficit in education, especially in communication instruction to high school students, especially, their proficiency in written communication as they extend to practical use.

Table 11. *Perceived Evaluation on the Level of Communication Skills of Junior Students by the School Administrators, Teachers and Students: Non Verbal Communication*

B. Non-Verbal Communication	School Administrators			Teachers			Students			Overall		
	N=9			N=24			N=220			N=253		
	WA	VI	RANK	WA	VI	RANK	WA	VI	RANK	WA	VI	R
1. Possess accurate and sufficient written communication for patient well-being and nurse protection	4.44	OP	6	3.92	OP	10.5	3.19	MP	12	3.85	OP	8
2. Exhibit effective and efficient communication process in:												
2.1 preparing report and recording	4.22	OP	10.5	3.88	OP	12	3.22	MP	9.5	3.77	OP	11
2.2 planning and implementation	4.22	OP	10.5	4.00	OP	8.5	3.23	MP	8	3.82	OP	10
2.3 evaluation process	4.34	OP	8	3.92	OP	10.5	3.22	MP	9.5	3.83	OP	9
3. Do not use abbreviation, jargon, meaningless phrases, irrelevant speculation, and offensive statements in preparation of reports	4.55	VP	4.5	4.08	OP	6	3.93	OP	2	4.19	OP	3
4. Seldom use electronic recording and communication tools in reporting methods	4.55	VP	4.5	4.24	OP	4	3.45	MP	6	4.08	OP	5
5. Render better accurate and appropriate effective communication	3.90	OP	12	4.00	OP	8.5	3.21	MP	7	3.70	OP	12
6. Are directed towards putting on records the patient-nurse communication	4.33	OP	7	4.20	OP	5	3.61	OP	4	4.05	OP	6
7. Use touch and body language approach	4.56	VP	2.5	4.28	OP	3	3.50	OP	5	4.11	OP	4
8. Observe congruence of normative ways of thinking and behaving	4.56	VP	2.5	4.04	OP	7	3.42	MP	7	4.01	OP	7
9. Include the family and “significant others”	4.67	VP	1	4.36	OP	1	3.85	OP	3	4.29	OP	1
10. Involve complex interactions between two or more members of different disciplines to meet holistic needs of patients	4.33	OP	9	4.32	OP	2	3.95	OP	1	4.20	OP	2
Overall	4.39	OP		4.10	OP		3.48	MP		3.99	OP	

Legend: 4.50-5.00 – Very Proficient (VP) | 3.50-4.49 – Often Proficient (OP) | 2.50-3.49 – Moderately Proficient (MP) | 1.50-2.49 – Least Proficient (LP) | 1.00-1.49 – Not Proficient (NP)

Paralanguage

Under this communication skills requirements as shown in Table 12, twelve (12) areas covered. The 12 areas covered under these skills, the school administrators evaluated 8 of the 12 areas of paralanguage skills to very proficient level. These are in are directed towards “giving emotions, feelings, attitude and comfort” showing the development of teacher-student relationship with 4.67 mean and was ranked 1.

The other areas under the same level of assessment were in skills were in require stressing appropriate words in reporting; and in demonstrate competence in stressing appropriate words with speed, volume and rhythm to stress concern also with 4.67 mean and were ranked 2. A product of information provision accenting or stressing different words that students need to transmit with openness

and honesty with 4.56, encourage students to actively participate in decision making regarding their own care and have strong felt need to decode and encode ideas using collaboration and teamwork, and in give faster vocal information concerning the students' performance are set within the context of the meanings between teacher-student relationship with 4.56 means each and were ranked 6.

Table 12. *Perceived Evaluation on the Level of Communication Skills of Junior Students by the School Administrators, Teachers and Students: Paralanguage*

<i>C. Para Language</i>	<i>School Administrators</i>			<i>Teachers</i>			<i>Students</i>			<i>Overall</i>		
	<i>N=9</i>			<i>N=24</i>			<i>N=220</i>			<i>N=253</i>		
	<i>WA</i>	<i>VI</i>	<i>RANK</i>	<i>WA</i>	<i>VI</i>	<i>RANK</i>	<i>WA</i>	<i>VI</i>	<i>RANK</i>	<i>WA</i>	<i>VI</i>	<i>RANK</i>
1. Are directed towards increased rate in instruction covering the instructional requirements	4.34	OP	11.5	4.36	OP	4.5	3.91	OP	5	4.20	OP	4.5
2. Give faster vocal information concerning the student performance	4.56	VP	6	4.48	OP	1	3.96	OP	1	4.33	OP	3
3. Are directed towards “giving emotions, feelings, attitude and comfort” showing the development of teacher-student relationship	4.67	VP	2	4.42	OP	2	3.95	OP	2.5	4.35	OP	1
4. Develop and enhance emotional comfort of students as reflected in:												
4.1 pleasant and positive feelings	4.34	OP	11.5	4.36	OP	4.5	3.86	OP	9	4.19	OP	6.5
4.2 a state of relaxation that affected the physical and emotional status of the body and positive feelings	4.44	OP	9.5	4.32	OP	7	3.85	OP	10	4.20	OP	4.5
5. A product of information provision accenting or stressing different words that teacher need to transmit with openness and honesty	4.56	VP	6	4.04	OP	10.5	3.93	OP	4	4.18	OP	8
6. Require stressing appropriate words in reporting of students' performance	4.67	VP	2	4.40	OP	3	3.95	OP	2.5	4.34	OP	2
7. Demonstrate competence in stressing appropriate words with speed, volume and rhythm to stress concern for students	4.67	VP	2	4.00	OP	12	3.89	OP	7	4.19	OP	6.5
8. Need to seek balance in the features of their interactions with students using verbal and non-verbal skills	4.44	OP	9.5	3.96	OP	13	3.88	OP	8	4.09	OP	11.5
9. Are set within the context of the meanings between teacher-student relationship	4.56	VP	6	4.32	OP	7	3.50	OP	12	4.13	OP	9
10. Encourage students to actively participate in decision making regarding their own care	4.56	VP	6	4.04	OP	10.5	3.75	OP	11	4.12	OP	10
11. Have strong felt need to decode and encode ideas using collaboration and teamwork	4.56	VP	6	4.28	OP	9	3.29	MP	13	4.05	OP	13
12. Increase need in the use of persuasion using intelligent and objective to affect communication transfer	4.04	OP	13	4.32	OP	7	3.90	OP	6	4.09	OP	11.5
Overall	4.49	VP		4.25	OP		3.82	OP		4.19	OP	

Legend: 4.50-5.00 – Very Proficient (VP) | 3.50-4.49 – Often Proficient (OP) | 2.50-3.49 – Moderately Proficient (MP) | 1.50-2.49 – Least Proficient (LP) | 1.00-1.49 – Not Proficient (NP)

Those which were rated to often proficient level were in need to seek balance in the features of their interactions with students using verbal and non-verbal skills, develop and enhance emotional comfort of students as reflected in pleasant and positive feelings, and in are directed towards increased rate in instruction covering the provision of practical instruction, and lastly, in increase need in the use of persuasion using intelligent and objective to affect communication transfer with 4.34 mean each which are all under the often level of proficiency.

Surprisingly, both the teachers and students evaluated this aspect of communication skills to have been exhibited to often proficient level, except in have strong felt need to decode and encode ideas using collaboration and teamwork which was evaluated moderately since it only obtained a weighted mean of 3.29 by the students.

For both groups of respondents, the highest obtained from 4.48 and 3.96 in give faster vocal information concerning the student performance by the teachers; and students were often proficient, to 3.98 and 3.50 for the second and third groups which obtained means were all described often.

The sums of 4.49 (school administrators); 4.25 (teachers) and 3.82 (students) were all under the often proficient level of verbal interpretation.

These findings on these specialized communication skills requirements seemed to meet the cognitive and emotional needs of the students according to McCabe (2014) who suggested the other communication skills required as relate to the teachers and students, need to not only go beyond since context of the meanings between teacher-student relationship, should also emphasize the collaborative and intelligent effort to effect clarity in communication transfer.

Specific Problem No. 4. Assessment on the Factors that Influence the Communication Skills of Junior High School Students in a Public High School in P. Garcia District, Batangas Province

There are eight (8) identified factors needed to effect effective transfer or communication skills of junior students. These are the findings of the surveys:

Teacher Professional Circumstance

Based on the average weighted means assigned to each of the areas under teacher professional circumstances, the school administrators very strongly agreed that eight (8) or half of the areas covered pose a very high impact on the communication skills of the junior high school students as expressed in as future professional, make commitment to interact directly and honestly with peers even if those interactions may be difficult and stressful with the highest obtained mean of 4.74 and was ranked 1. Ranked 2.5 were in I will consider the situation before taking any action, and I will take time to organize my thoughts and make my deliverable as concise and clean as possible with 4.72 followed by I will gather and confirm information before making a decision, and listening is a vital part of communications – I shall make sure that I listen to my teachers and peers, not just hear them with 4.69; I am an open-minded person and willing to change behaviour and communication preference to accommodate those around me with 4.62; I will focus on problems, not personalities with 4.56; and I shall get to know the people you work with and let them know that you care about them as individuals with 4.51.

Table 13. Assessment on the Factors that Influence the Communication Skills of Junior High School Students: Teacher Professional Circumstances

Teacher Professional Circumstances	School Administrators			Teachers			Students			Overall		
	N=9			N=24			N=220			N=253		
	WA	VI	RANK	WA	VI	RANK	WA	VI	RANK	WA	VI	RANK
1. I am an open minded person and willing to change behavior and communication preference to accommodate those around me	4.62	VSA	6	3.99	SA	14	3.98	SA	1	4.19	SA	10
2. I will not jump to conclusion about the motivation of my co-teachers	4.46	SA	11	3.65	SA	15	3.90	SA	6	4.01	SA	15
3. I am not the type to react defensively when co-workers or disagree with me	4.49	SA	9.5	3.57	SA	16	3.48	MA	16	3.85	SA	16
4. While much interaction with co-teachers will take place in the work setting, I believe that taking advantage of opportunities to interact on a more personal level can help improve relationship	4.33	SA	15	4.29	SA	8	3.89	SA	7.5	4.17	SA	11
5. One of the benefits of interacting with others, especially those with different opinions or backgrounds is the ability to broaden perspective as they begin to understand other viewpoints	4.41	SA	12.5	4.23	SA	9	3.50	SA	15	4.05	SA	14
6. I make commitment to interact directly and honestly with peers even if those interactions may be difficult and stressful	4.74	VSA	1	4.57	VSA	2	3.80	SA	13	4.37	SA	1
7. I will consider the situation before taking any action	4.72	VSA	2.5	4.44	SA	6.5	3.75	SA	14	4.30	SA	4
8. I will gather and confirm	4.69	VSA	4.5	4.08	SA	12	3.95	SA	2.5	4.24	SA	8

information before making a decision													
9. I will focus on problems, not personalities	4.56	VSA	7	4.45	SA	5	3.85	SA	11	4.29	SA	5	
10. Whatever the stage of my career, I should continue to learn	4.49	SA	9.5	4.58	VSA	1	3.95	SA	2.5	4.34	SA	2.5	
11. I must be sensitive to different cultural background, sexual orientations, marriage statuses and age groups	4.41	SA	12	4.13	SA	11	3.93	SA	4	4.16	SA	12	
12. I will take time to organize my thoughts and make my deliverable as concise and clean as possible	4.72	VSA	2.5	4.14	SA	10	3.89	SA	7.5	4.25	SA	7	
13. I shall be aware of the message I am giving with my body language	4.08	SA	16	4.46	SA	4	3.83	SA	12	4.12	SA	12	
14. I shall observe how individuals interact with one another since everyone has this own workplace culture – and way of doing things	4.36	SA	14	4.01	SA	12.5	3.91	SA	5	4.09	SA	13	
15. Listening is a vital part of communications – I shall make sure that I listen to my administrators, and peers and students, not just hear them	4.69	VSA	4.5	4.49	SA	3	3.85	SA	10	4.34	SA	2.5	
16. I shall get to know the people I work with and let them know that I care about them as individuals	4.51	VSA	8	4.44	SA	6.5	3.87	SA	9	4.28	SA	6	
	Overall	4.52	VSA	4.22	SA		3.83	SA		4.19	SA		

Legend: 4.50-5.00 – Very Strongly Agree (VSA) | 3.50-4.49 – Strongly Agree (SA) | 2.50-3.49 – Moderately Agree (MA) | 1.50-2.49 – Least Agree (LA) | 1.00-1.49 – Very Strongly Disagree (VSD)

The other areas, they strongly agreed that these teacher professional circumstances also pose a moderate influence in communication performance of students as proofs of obtained means of 4.49 each were in I am not the type to react defensively when co-teachers or disagree with me; 4.46 in I will not jump into conclusion about the motivation of my co-teachers; 4.41 each in one of the benefits of interacting with others, especially those with different opinions or background is the ability to broaden perspective as they begin to understand other viewpoints, and in I must be sensitive to different cultural background, sexual orientations, marriage statuses and age groups; 4.33 in while much interaction with co-workers will take place in the work setting, I believe that taking advantage of opportunities to interact on a more personal level can help improve relationship; and 4.08 in I shall be aware of the message am giving with my body language.

On the contrary, the teachers had very strongly agreed that teacher professional circumstances exhibited in whatever the stage of the career, I should continue to learn with 4.58; as a future educator, I make commitment to interact directly and honestly with peers even if those interactions may be difficult and stressful with 4.57 very highly influence the communication skills of the junior high students; and only agreed strongly on the other 14 areas as reflected in the obtained means from 4.49 in listening is a vital part of communication – I shall make sure that I listen to my teachers and peers, not just hear them, to 3.65 in I will not jump into conclusion about the motivation of my co-workers.

However, the student respondents only strongly agreed that the teacher professional circumstances demonstrated by the administrators and faculty were evident in 15 areas, from 3.98 in I am an open-minded person and willing to change behaviour and communication preference to accommodate those around me, to one of the benefits of interacting with others, especially those with different opinions or backgrounds is the ability to broaden perspective as they begin to understand other viewpoints with 3.50 mean, but only moderately demonstrated in I am not the type to react defensively when co-teachers or disagree with me with 3.48 men.

In summary, the differences in the assessments were noted strongly as the first group demonstrated very strongly that teacher professional competence to impact the communication skills of their students with overall mean of 4.52, but only strongly agreed by the teachers with 4.22; and the junior high school student respondents with 3.83 weighted mean.

These findings were strongly in support Vethamani and Rahman (2015) on the impact of effective communication skills required of teachers as they interrelate themselves to their students since the same reflect the quality of instruction – effectively and efficiently, job satisfaction and communication skills of future professionals in the case of students.

Teacher Advocate

Under this aspect, nine (9) major areas and six (6) subareas are enumerated in Table 14. The same three (3) groups of respondents assessed their levels of agreement from very strongly agree to very strongly disagree.

A scrutiny of the table showed both the school administrators and teachers very strongly agreed that teacher advocate was very significant factor that influenced communication skills of junior high school students.

These were found in the nine (9) areas as assessed by the school administrators where the highest obtained means were in I shall assist and facilitate communication promotion (4.79), in I must be receptive to the students concerns, questions, and fears and when the students are unable to communicate their needs effectively, it is my role to act on their behalf and support their choices with 4.77, and to be effective and successful teacher, I must focus exclusively on the students’ needs and I must show compassion and understanding which are vital in being an advocate (4.74), respectively. These were positioned from 1 to 4.5, respectively.

The other teacher advocate requirements were likewise assessed to highest level as from I shall empower my students. Our goals for those we care for are to alleviate pain and suffering, increase their sense of independence and self control, and guide them towards a path of living a healthy lifestyle and I shall bear in mind that I am /to help to prevent or manage suffering – whether physical, emotional or psychological – is perhaps the most important aspect of care from the students’ perspective with 4.72 means, to 4.59 mean in I shall bear in mind that I am /to provide care for all students with the same degree of compassion and professionalism, without allowing personal biases to influence their practice, respectively ranked 6.5 to 13.

The teachers, equally, seemed to share the assessments of their superiors since out of nine (9) areas covered, 7 or 78 percent were on very strong level of agreement I must show compassion and understanding which are vital in being an advocate with 4.71, to 4.51 in when the students are too sick or unable to communicate their needs effectively, it is my role to act on their behalf and support their choices and I shall bear in mind that I am /to help to prevent or manage their physical, emotional or psychological – is perhaps the most important aspect of care from the students’ perspective; and then strongly agreed on areas in I shall bear in mind that I am /to act as a communicator, liaison, educator, interpreter and caregiver with 4.38 weighted mean.

On the contrary, the students very strongly agreed that they had eight (8) major and subareas covered from 4.65 to 4.50; and the remaining areas were assessed to strong level of assessment.

On the whole, the overall obtained means of 4.69 (school administrators) and 4.52 (teachers) indicate very strong agreement that teacher advocate is a major indicator in the nursing communication skills. On the contrary, the student respondents perceived their agreement to only strongly agreed level.

These findings confirm what Doyle (2012) stressed that communication skills should not only be client-centered, but also an integral part of the teacher advocate since the same serves as the strong foundation in developing high quality nursing care, both delivered orally/verbally and non-verbally, even using paralanguage technique to effect excellent transmission of message.

Table 14. Assessment on the Factors that Influence the Communication Skills of Junior High School Students: Teacher Advocate

Teacher Advocate	School Administrators			Teachers			Students			Overall		
	N=9			N=24			N=220			N=253		
	WA	VI	RANK	WA	VI	RANK	WA	VI	RANK	WA	VI	RANK
1. To be effective and successful nurse, I must focus exclusively on the students' needs	4.74	VSA	4.5	4.65	VSA	3	4.63	VSA	2	4.68	VSA	2.5
2. It is my job to be their voice when students feel like they are not being heard. As professionals, we must protect their rights and welfare	4.64	VSA	10.5	4.49	SA	11	4.40	SA	12	4.51	VSA	12
3. I must show compassion and understanding which are vital in being an advocate	4.74	VSA	4.5	4.71	VSA	1	4.65	VSA	1	4.70	VSA	1
4. I must be receptive to the students concerns, questions, and fears	4.77	VSA	2.5	4.55	VSA	8	4.59	VSA	3	4.64	VSA	4
5. When the students are unable to communicate their needs effectively, it is my role to act on their behalf and support their choices	4.64	VSA	10.5	4.51	VSA	9.5	4.47	SA	11	4.54	VSA	10.5
6. Students’ best interests must be my first priority, one hundred percent of the time	4.77	VSA	2.5	4.00	SA	14	3.70	SA	14	4.16	SA	14
7. I shall assist and facilitate student promotion	4.79	VSA	1	4.67	VSA	2	4.58	VSA	4	4.68	VSA	2.5
8. I shall empower mystudents. Our goals to increase their sense	4.72	VSA	6.5	4.61	VSA	4.5	4.40	SA	13	4.57	VSA	7

of independence and self control, and guide them towards a path of living independently

9. I shall bear in mind that I am /to:

9.1 in a position to integrate all aspects of the students care and ensure that concerns are addressed, standards of care are met and a positive outcome for the patient remains the goal of the healthcare team	4.56	VSA	14	4.57	VSA	7	4.52	VSA	6	4.55	VSA	9
9.2 provide care for all patients with the same degree of compassion and professionalism, without allowing personal biases to influence their practice	4.59	VSA	13	4.58	VSA	6	4.51	VSA	7	4.56	VSA	8
9.3 help to prevent or manage physical, emotional or psychological – is perhaps the most important aspect of care from the students' perspective	4.72	VSA	6.5	4.51	VSA	9.5	4.56	VSA	5	4.60	VSA	5.5
9.4 provide emotional support, or simply offer a friendly ear that requires commitment on the students' total development	4.69	VSA	8	4.61	VSA	4.5	4.50	VSA	8	4.60	VSA	5.5
9.5 act as a communicator, liaison, educator, interpreter and caregiver	4.67	VSA	9	4.46	SA	12	4.48	SA	10	4.54	VSA	10.5
9.6 advocate to help navigate the unfamiliar education communication and facilitate communication among teachers and students	4.62	VSA	12	4.38	SA	13	4.49	VSA	9	4.50	VSA	13
Overall	4.69	VSA		4.52	VSA		4.46	SA		4.56	VSA	

Legend: 4.50-5.00 – Very Strongly Agree (VSA) | 3.50-4.49 – Strongly Agree (SA) | 2.50-3.49 – Moderately Agree (MA) | 1.50-2.49 – Least Agree (LA) | 1.00-1.49 – Very Strongly Disagree (VSD)

Student Advocate

Table 15 presents the 12 areas covered under student advocate which ranges from it is important to clarify the plan with students, to teachers need to be aware of their body language and use of personal space when talking with students.

According to the assessment of the school administrators, ten (10) of the 12 areas under the domain were very highly agreed assessment as reflected in the obtained means of 4.85 each and the highest among the areas in good communication is a core academic skills, and good teacher-student communication improves patients' health outcomes, succeeded by even though cohesiveness is a desirable state for students to learn, there is little an individual member can do to promote it, and teachers and other educators must work to collaborate more effectively (4.82) each; acknowledging the patient's experience is not necessary in teacher-student relationships; and teachers need to be aware of their body language and use of personal space when talking with students (4.74) each; it is important to clarify the treatment plan with students, and giving information about lifestyle is important in instruction (4.72) each; addressing students' emotions and psychological issues is absolutely essential in education today (4.59), respectively.

Those where they strongly agreed that communication skills influence how they advocate student welfare were in dealing with the emotional problems of students is the responsibility of psychiatrists, psychologists and social workers, not teachers (3.92); and students are generally unaffected by teachers' nonverbal responses (3.56).

It seemed that the teacher respondents very strongly shared the assessments of their school administrators since they perceived very strongly the influence of possessing communication skills in advocating student welfare in nine (9) areas from the highest means of 4.77 in good communication is a core instructional skills, to 4.55 in giving information about lifestyle is important in instructional practice; and the remaining three (3) areas were either strong and moderately assessed in students are generally unaffected by teachers' nonverbal responses with 3.48 mean.

Finally, true to their assessments, the student respondents also shared very strongly advocating student welfare through effective communication in eight (8) areas; strongly in two (2) areas; and moderately showed with their teachers the area in students are generally unaffected by teachers' nonverbal responses. The overall obtained means of 4.59 by the first and 4.51 by the second very strongly expressed very strong agreement the influence of possessing communication skills in advocating student welfare which was not shared

by the third group since, they only strongly (4.46) support the impact of the skills required in the future teacher-student interrelationship with their prospective students.

Table 15. Assessment on the Factors that Influence the Communication Skills of Junior High School Students: Student Advocate

Student Advocate	School Administrators			Faculty			Students			Overall		
	N=39			N=84			N=220			N=343		
	WA	VI	RANK	WA	VI	RANK	WA	VI	RANK	WA	VI	RANK
1. It is important to clarify the instructional plan with students	4.72	VSA	8.5	4.71	VSA	3.5	4.65	VSA	4	4.70	VSA	4
2. Checking for students' understanding is generally necessary	4.79	VSA	5	4.60	VSA	7.5	4.65	VSA	5	4.68	VSA	5.5
3. Even though cohesiveness is a desirable state for the team, there is little an individual member can do to promote it	4.82	VSA	3.5	4.45	SA	10	4.63	VSA	6	4.63	VSA	7
4. Good communication is a core skills	4.85	VSA	1.5	4.77	VSA	1	4.68	VSA	1	4.77	VSA	1
5. Education professionals must work to collaborate more effectively	4.82	VSA	3.5	4.71	VSA	3.5	4.60	VSA	7	4.71	VSA	3
6. Acknowledging the students experience is necessary in teacher-student relationships	4.74	VSA	6.5	4.21	SA	11	4.14	SA	11	4.36	SA	10
7. Dealing with the emotional problems of patients is the responsibility of psychiatrists, psychologists an social workers, not nurses	3.92	SA	11	4.60	VSA	7.5	4.52	VSA	8	4.35	SA	11
8. Giving information about lifestyle is important in education	4.72	VSA	8.5	4.55	VSA	9	4.48	SA	10	4.58	VSA	8
9. Addressing studnets' emotions and psychological issues is absolutely essential in education today	4.59	VSA	10	4.63	VSA	6	4.50	VSA	9	4.57	VSA	9
10. Good teacher-student communication improves students performance	4.85	VSA	1.5	4.75	VSA	2	4.67	VSA	2.5	4.75	VSA	2
11. Students are generally affected by teachers' nonverbal responses	3.56	SA	12	3.48	MA	12	3.35	MA	12	3.46	MA	12
12. Teachers need to be aware of their body language and use of personal space when talking with students	4.74	VSA	6.5	4.64	VSA	5	4.67	VSA	2.5	4.68	VSA	5.5
Overall	4.59	VSA		4.51	VSA		4.46	SA		4.52	VSA	

Legend: 4.50-5.00 – Very Strongly Agree (VSA) | 3.50-4.49 – Strongly Agree (SA) | 2.50-3.49 – Moderately Agree (MA) | 1.50-2.49 – Least Agree (LA) | 1.00-1.49 – Very Strongly Disagree (VSD)

Teamwork

The dynamics of teamwork in influencing effective communication skills is best demonstrated when stakeholders get together to meet the individual needs, especially, among students' increased knowledge, interpersonal and practical skills to effect greater understanding of the importance of communication as the key element in the application of teacher-student relationship and intervention.

Eight (8) areas are covered in the domain which include from demonstrate knowledge and family to use communication and interpersonal relationship skills, to prove ability to provide/ receive constructive feedback and recognition to/ from fellow members.

To the school administrators, they very strongly agreed teamwork very much influence the communication skills of the students. These assessments were also shared by the teacher respondents.

These were highlighted in Table 16 where both groups of respondents expressed jointly their perceptions and even their preferences. Both very strongly agreed that teamwork was very much evident in show ability to articulate and promote, and display ability to follow proper channels which was ranked 1.5 (4.85) and ranked 1 and 2, while the first ranked teamwork in demonstrate ability to actively participate in team activities to plan, implement, and evaluate student care with 4.79 and 4.65 means, teamwork in demonstrate respect

for the knowledge, skills, ideas, opinions, and expertise of all members of the team with 4.79 mean by the first group was ranked 3.5, but was ranked 7.5 by the second group with 4.54.

Table 16. Assessment on the Factors that Influence the Communication Skills of Junior High School Students: Teamwork

Teamwork	School Administrators			Teachers			Students			Overall		
	N=9			N=24			N=220			N=253		
	WA	VI	RANK	WA	VI	RANK	WA	VI	RANK	WA	VI	RANK
1. Demonstrate knowledge and ability to use communication and interpersonal relationship skills	4.69	VSA	8	4.69	VSA	3	4.45	SA	4.5	4.61	VSA	4
2. Possess knowledge to describe the roles of a team member in forming and maintaining an effective teacher-student relationship	4.74	VSA	6	4.54	VSA	7.5	4.50	VSA	3	4.59	VSA	7
3. Demonstrate respect for the knowledge, skill, ideas, opinions, and expertise of all members of the team	4.79	VSA	3.5	4.54	VSA	7.5	4.45	SA	4.5	4.59	VSA	7
4. Exhibit ability to promote group cohesiveness by contributing the purposes and goals of the team	4.77	VSA	5	4.61	VSA	6	4.43	SA	6.5	4.60	VSA	5
5. Demonstrate ability to actively participate in team activities to plan, implement, and evaluate student performance	4.79	VSA	3.5	4.65	VSA	4	4.42	SA	8	4.62	VSA	3
6. Show ability to articulate and promote the role of the teachers	4.85	VSA	1.5	4.74	VSA	1	4.57	VSA	1	4.72	VSA	1
7. Display ability to follow proper channels of communication within the school	4.85	VSA	1.5	4.71	VSA	2	4.52	VSA	2	4.69	VSA	2
8. Prove ability to provide/receive constructive feedback and recognition to/ from fellow team members	4.72	VSA	7	4.62	VSA	5	4.43	SA	6.5	4.59	VSA	7
Overall	4.78	VSA		4.64	VSA		4.47	SA		4.63	VSA	

Legend: 4.50-5.00 – Very Strongly Agree (VSA) | 3.50-4.49 – Strongly Agree (SA) | 2.50-3.49 – Moderately Agree (MA) | 1.50-2.49 – Least Agree (LA) | 1.00-1.49 – Very Strongly Disagree (VSD)

Nonetheless, teamwork shown in demonstrate ability to actively participate in team activities to plan, implement, and evaluate student care with 4.79 by the first group with rank of 3.5 was closely ranked 4 by the second group. Closely, while the first ranked 7 teamwork in prove ability to provide, receive constructive feedback and recognition to/ from fellow team members with 4.72, the second group ranked it 4.62, still on the very high level of agreement. The teamwork in possess knowledge to describe the roles of a team member in forming and maintaining an effective team, and demonstrate respect for the knowledge, skills, ideas, opinions, and expertise of all members of the team with 4.54, the last in rank by the second also ranked last or 8 by the first group with 4.74.

On the contrary, the students seemed to express varied reactions to the aspect since they assessed very strongly in show ability to articulate and promote, and display ability to follow proper channels with 4.57 and 4.52 mean; and strongly agreed in six (6) teamwork requirements where the highest means are from 4.45 each in demonstrate knowledge and ability to use communication and interpersonal relationship skills, and demonstrate respect for the knowledge, skills, ideas, opinions, and expertise of all members of the team, to demonstrate ability to actively participate in team activities to plan, implement, and evaluate client care with a mean of 4.42.

Summarily, the overall weighted means of 4.78 and 4.64 for the first and second group with very strong agreement, was only strongly agreed by the students with 4.47 overall mean. These findings further confirm what McCabe (2017) endorsed the collaborative, reciprocal nature or simply, teamwork in training and communicating of students to their administrators, teachers, and even the other stakeholders as well as their significant others in creating warm relationship between and among themselves, and the others to achieve the desired results.

Effective Communication

An analysis of Table 17 on the five (5) major areas covered by the domain has also nine (9) sub-areas perceived from very strong to strong level of agreement.

Since both the school administrators and teachers very strongly confirmed that all the five (5) areas in the factors influence the communication skills of the students in exhibits knowledge and ability to assess and manage clients in states of disorientation,

confusion, mental illness, or impairment with obtained highest means of 4.71 (teachers) and 4.85 (school administrators), the students seemed to contradict this assessment since they only strongly agreed with 4.35 and all ranked the same area as the highest. The same assessment was expressed in demonstrate ability to identify and apply appropriate communication techniques also with 4.85 and 4.64 for the first and the second group, but only strongly agreed with 4.29 by the third group, however, the areas took the second rank among the 5 areas covered.

Third in the overall rank was in illustrate knowledge and ability to document using behavioural description, the students' communication pattern, therapies used, and outcomes which was very strongly shared assessments of the school administrators (4.77) and teachers (4.61), but only strongly perceived by the students (4.25).

These areas were all on the highest level of assessments by the groups of respondents.

Table 17. Assessment on the Factors that Influence the Communication Skills of Junior High School Students: Effective Communication

Effective Communication	School Administrators			Teachers			Students			Overall		
	N=9			N=24			N=220			N=253		
	WA	VI	RANK	WA	VI	RANK	WA	VI	RANK	WA	VI	RANK
1. Demonstrate ability to identify and apply appropriate communication techniques	4.85	VSA	1.5	4.64	VSA	2	4.29	SA	2	4.59	VSA	2
2. Show ability to use alternative communication techniques to create a therapeutic relationship in:												
2.1 Cultural/religious	4.74	VSA	5.5	4.58	VSA	6	4.13	SA	8	4.49	SA	4.5
2.2 Hearing loss	4.72	VSA	7.5	4.58	VSA	6	4.05	SA	11	4.45	SA	8.5
2.3 Language barriers	4.69	VSA	9.5	4.55	VSA	9.5	4.19	SA	6.5	4.48	SA	6
2.4 Mental impairment	4.74	VSA	5.5	4.51	VSA	12	4.10	SA	9	4.45	SA	8.5
2.5 Physical impairment	4.72	VSA	7.5	4.55	VSA	9.5	4.06	SA	10	4.44	SA	10
2.6 Speech and language impairment	4.77	VSA	3.5	4.61	VSA	3.5	3.99	SA	12	4.46	SA	7
3. Exhibit knowledge and ability to assess and manage students in states of disorientation, confusion, mental illness, or impairment	4.85	VSA	1.5	4.71	VSA	1	4.35	SA	1	4.64	VSA	1
4. Display knowledge and ability to provide therapeutic techniques such as:												
4.1 reality orientation	4.38	SA	12	4.57	VSA	8	4.24	SA	5	4.40	SA	12
4.2 validation therapy	4.69	VSA	9.5	4.58	VSA	6	4.19	SA	6.5	4.49	SA	4.5
4.3 reminiscence therapy	4.46	SA	11	4.54	VSA	11	4.26	SA	3	4.42	SA	11
5. Illustrate knowledge and ability to document using behavioral description, the client's communication pattern, therapies used, and outcomes	4.77	VSA	3.5	4.61	VSA	3.5	4.25	SA	4	4.54	VSA	3
Overall	4.70	VSA		4.59	VSA		4.18	SA		4.49	SA	

Legend: 4.50-5.00 – Very Strongly Agree (VSA) | 3.50-4.49 – Strongly Agree (SA) | 2.50-3.49 – Moderately Agree (MA) | 1.50-2.49 – Least Agree (LA) | 1.00-1.49 – Very Strongly Disagree (VSD)

The remaining three (3) areas of the domain were only agreed upon that influence the communication skills of the nursing students in acquiring knowledge and ability to provide therapeutic techniques and in showing ability to use alternative communication techniques, and even in the students' ability to assess.

Ultimately, both the school administrators (4.70) and teachers (4.59) very strongly agreed on the significance of teamwork in adhering the communication skills of the students, the student respondents only strongly agreed (4.18) that this will impact strongly their ability to network and collaborate if they are well-equipped and trained to the requirements in the practice of the profession. These data were further profounded by El-Helou (2016) that accurate communication as the heart of the education process should be taught to the students who, in the future, will be part of teams who will take care of their students.

Specific Problem No. 5. Significant Difference Between the Level of Communication Skills of Junior High School Students and Their Selected Demographic Profile

The Chi-square (X²) statistics was used to test for significant difference between the level of communication skills of the junior high school students and their selected demographic profile.

The matrix for the results of the application of the statistical tool is presented in Table 20 using the S.P.S.S. for Windows in:

Gender

A scan at Table 18 on the frequency distribution of groups of responses for a total of 101 male and 152 female respondents or a row total of 253.

The results of X² treatment from the six (6) frequency grouping for male and female showed very significant difference between the perceived assessments of the groups of respondents on the communication skills; and when they are grouped according to gender as evidenced by the obtained computed X² = 17.162 which value is much higher (>) than its critical F = 5.99, thus, reject the research hypothesis (H₀) of no significant difference at 0.05 alpha level.

Table 18. *Significant Difference Between the Level of Communication Skills of Junior High School Students and Their Selected Personal Profile According to Gender*

Frequency	X values		Computed X Values
2	44.979	-6.979	1.083
7	42.653	17.347	7.055
7	45.367	-10.367	2.369
17	71.020	6.979	0.686
92	67.347	-17.347	4.468
128	71.633	10.367	1.500

Computed Chi-square (X²) values 17.162

Critical Chi-square (X²) value 5.99

Interpretation/ Decision Very Significant: Reject null H₀

Significant Level 0.05

Civil Status

Table 19 features the frequency distribution of the nine (9) sets of variables of civil status of the respondents against their assessments on the level of perceived communication skills of nursing students.

Table 19. *Significant Difference Between the Level of Communication Skills of Junior High School Students and Their Selected Personal Profile According to Civil Status*

Frequency	X values		Computed X Values
1	15.219	-5.219	1.789
8	14.431	-1.431	0.142
0	15.349	6.650	2.881
8	100.443	5.557	0.307
15	95.248	1.752	0.032
1	101.309	-7.309	0.527
209	0.338	-0.338	0.338
11	0.321	-0.321	0.321
0	0.341	0.659	1.273

Computed Chi-square (X²) values 2.799

Critical Chi-square (X²) value 9.79

Interpretation/ Decision Not Significant: Accept null H₀

Significant Level 0.05

Testing for the same research H₀ and statistical tool, the data result to an overall computed X² = 2.799 which is much lesser (<) than its critical X² = 9.79, thus, accept the H₀ of no significant difference between two (2) sets of variables since the obtained value is in the acceptance region at 0.05 alpha level.

These findings acknowledge the need for the students to develop and improve their communication skills directed at meeting the cognitive and practical skills, irregardless of status, Finsrud (2017) felt that the significance of communication skills related to student performance, and efficacy of delivery of should not be underestimated.

Age Range

This demographic profile consists of 24 sets of variables which sets of data are presented in Table 20. There are 25 frequency responses the three (3) types of communication, from oral and verbal communication, to paralanguage approach.

The obtained X² values were subjected to final treatment and result to a computed X² = 24.755 which is found in the rejection region since the computed value exceeds the significant level.

Exploring further the influence of age range to the communication skills of the students which point out the variance of rejection that age range, indeed, validate the value of knowledge and skills in communication, specifically, the competence very much needed by junior high school students using verbal and oral as well as non-verbal communication to effect delivery of quality instruction and

practice.

Table 20. *Significant Difference Between the Level of Communication Skills of Junior High School Students and Their Selected Personal Profile According to Age Range*

Frequency	<i>X</i> values	Computed <i>X</i> Values
0	67.300	-15.300
0	63.819	7.181
1	67.880	8.119
2	9.131	7.869
3	8.659	-3.659
1	9.210	-4.210
1	10.146	-0.146
1	9.621	0.379
0	10.233	-0.233
2	9.808	2.192
10	9.300	2.699
4	9.892	-4.8922
6	12.851	2.149
1	12.187	-4.187
1	12.962	2.038
0	3.720	2.280
199	3.528	-1.528
21	3.752	-0.752
0	2.367	0.633
0	2.245	0.245
0	2.388	-0.388
0	0.676	0.324
0	0.642	-0.641
0	0.682	0.318

Computed Chi-square (*X*²) values 24.755

Critical Chi-square (*X*²) value 23.68

Interpretation/ Decision Not Significant: Accept null *H*₀

Significant Level 0.05

Conclusions

Based on these findings, the following conclusions are drawn:

The respondents of the study were female-dominated education practitioners/ administrators, teachers, and students, young and aggressive as they possessed the minimum requirements of their present position and have served for quite a number of years in their school.

Literary instructional approach was used to great extent in the teaching of Communication Arts English as proof of obtained composite mean of 3.59.

The Communication skills of the junior high students were assessed to often proficient level as proof of composite mean of 4.14.

The school should focus on teaching the different phases of communication skills. Achieving organizational goal is all about communication – clarifying, motivating, team dynamics, sense-making, negotiation, presenting and influencing and building feedback loops. Building interpersonal relationships is foundational to the success of teaching. Some of the most important aspects of communication take the form of listening and showing gratitude, which is the key in the role. This can take many forms including sending a card, an email acknowledgment, a handwritten note, a phone call or special recognition. Practicing and learning key written and verbal communication strategies with the notion of using key words at key times is essential to the development of any communicative skills.

The groups of respondents strongly agreed that there were the factors that influenced the communication skills of high school students as reflected by the composite mean of 4.48 where the influence of teamwork, teacher advocate and effective communication was found.

There exists no significant difference in the assessments of the school administrators, teachers, and junior high students on the desired level of communication skills of high school students.

There exists a significant difference between the level of communication skills of the junior high students and when they are grouped according to their gender and age range, hence, reject null *H*₀, but accept in civil status set at different critical *t* and at 0.05 alpha level.

The Proposed Communication Skills Program for Junior High School Students, will serve as a guide for administrators and teachers in the area of instructional competence in the teaching of Communication Arts English subject.

Based from the conclusions drawn, the following are the recommendations offered:

Review the hiring and selection of teachers to include proficiency in communication to facilitate instruction, research and evidence-based practice. It must be at the heart of professional teaching standards and recognized by all those involved as fundamental to high quality, instructional approach.

Provide realistic expectations of the roles and functions of teachers handling Communication Arts English. Some of the most highly rated competencies including instructional strategies in literary and communication be included in the teaching of reading, oral and verbal and non-verbal communication arts subjects to prepare junior high students to the complex communication challenges they will confront in the practice of their profession.

There should be an extra effort on the part of the school administrators and teachers to attend to special training and development seminars/ workshops or communication and communication skills competencies so they can better position themselves on how to proceed with the teaching of literature and the different phases of communication arts. This instrument could be deemed useful in the development of skills literary and communication arts programs tailored to organizational needs of teachers and students.

These institutions should focus on teaching the different literary approach and phases of communication skills. Achieving organizational goal is all about communication – clarifying, motivating, team dynamics, sense-making, negotiation, presenting and influencing and building feedback loops. Building interpersonal relationships is also foundational to the success of instructional practice. Some of the most important aspects of communication take the form of listening and showing gratitude, which is the key in the role. This can take many forms including sending a card, an email acknowledgment, a handwritten note, a phone call or special recognition. Practicing and learning key written and verbal communication strategies with the notion of using key words at key times is essential to the development of effective communication.

The school under study should move towards a more goal – and service-oriented approach using literary approach and skills in communication, especially, in the area of critical-thinking, and evidence-based practice where a lot of oral and verbal and non-verbal communication is wanting. Communication seems to be one different aspect in instruction and practice because it demands a lot of discussion, critical thinking, problem-solving and reporting. Equipping the students with knowledge and skills in all aspects of the communication process will greatly help them to achieve success in their chosen profession.

Channel the Institutions' best communication skills practices towards creating and building the Literary and Communication Skills Program for Junior High School Students, horizontally and vertically, integrating them by way of literary and communication skills instruction and practical application as well as sustaining the program through training endeavors to ensure without let-ups, quality instruction and quality programs that redound to quality graduates.

Further research linking literary and communicative competencies with emphasis on output is necessary in today's outcome-driven environment. Driving towards academic excellence and outcomes is a discussion of the institutions today and further work is needed to determine which concepts and literacy and skills competencies have significant impact on the student outcomes.

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